

COMPARISON OF 3D SCANNING TECHNIQUES AND PHOTOGRAMMETRY TOOLS

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Abstract

Digital reproduction of complex shapes, such as fossils, skulls, sculptures, and other flowing geometries, is difficult. Optical methods such as 3D scanning and photogrammetry allow for capturing such complex geometry that is nearly impossible to reproduce otherwise. Once 3D models are available, rapid prototyping (3D printing) allows for scalable and reproducible models quite easily. Three methods of capturing these geometries were evaluated in this study: two scanning systems and one photogrammetric camera software. The Revopoint 3D POP is a structured light scanner used in conjunction with a PC or mobile device, utilizing feature detection as the scanner is moved around the object, capturing a reasonable level of detail at the cost of an unrefined mesh. The Matter and Form V2 3D Scanner uses a built-in turntable to scan subjects with a laser line as they rotate. The multiple scans captured were merged to form a single digital model. 3DF Zephyr is a photogrammetry software used to build a digital model from a series of photographs taken of the sample in question. Digital photos were taken using an Olympus OM-D E-M5II in a rising spiral fashion and then combined to create a 3D digital model. Human faces, statues, and concrete fragments were used to evaluate these techniques. The final results were 3D printed on the Ender 3 V2 for visual comparison. The goal was to increase the use of 3D scanning technology available to the university community.

Introduction

As engineers, the environment one operates in is important in most, if not all, applications. One way to visualize this working environment is to model it, most commonly using computer aided drafting (CAD) programs, such as Solidworks or Autodesk products. However, complex geometries can arise that prolong this modeling process and produce errors in these models that can complicate the design process down the road. To mitigate this problem, accurate models can be created using alternate means, such as scanning and photogrammetry. Fields ranging from biology and medicine to criminology and real estate all utilize this skill to recreate entities for research, law enforcement, business, and more. These methods are also used in aerospace, automotive, video game, and other industries to produce fast and accurate three-dimensional models. One outlet for these models is 3D printing, whether it be a resin or fused deposition modeling (FDM) printer to reproduce these items in miniature to larger sizes.

In the early stages of this study, a literature review was conducted to find papers discussing the scanners and methods used, but most papers only considered one system to objects

but not each other. In this current study, the author hoped to broaden interest in advanced 3D modeling tools, find a relatively cheap solution for universities to invest in, and show multiple objects being scanned by the three products and how they compared. The goal of this study was not to test the manufacturer's claims on the precision of the digitized model produced but rather to report the possibilities and limitations of each system.

Criteria

In this paper, the author covers a series of scanners that were procured at different price points. The Revopoint POP 3D (Revopoint, 2021) is at the lower end of the price range observed, at approximately \$550, with the Matter and Form V2 scanner (Matter and Form, 2018) bringing the middle up to a price of \$750. Finally, photogrammetry is rather fluid in terms of hardware and software costs. The free version of the 3DF Zephyr software (3DF Zephyr, 2022) was used for photogrammetry in conjunction with an Olympus OM-D E-M5II camera with a Panasonic Lumix G Vario 1:3.5-5.6/14-42mm lens. The total cost was estimated to be approximately \$1000. This range was chosen as it was decided to be a small investment for labs or student prototyping centers to spend for future endeavors in 3D modeling and printing. After acquiring a point cloud of the subject, it would then be exported out to a Standard Tessellation Language format (also known as a .stl file) where it would be processed by Ultimaker Cura (Braam, 2022) with presets of a 0.16mm-layer height and a set in fill of 30% Gyroid. All the models produced were compared after being printed on an Ender-3 V2 with the same modifications used on all prints, including an upgraded bed, leveled printing surface, and upgraded aluminum extruder. Supports generated by Cura were removed and any residual markings from the removal tools or process were then blended with the rest of the model via light exposure to heat introduced by a blowtorch. Filament and hue were kept constant using MatterHackers red polylactic acid (PLA) for most models, but variants in color appeared in some cases and were concluded to not impact the comparison of the models. Additionally, differences in the coloration of 3D models were present but impacted results superficially.

Background

3D scanners work using the principle of emitting a light that can reflect off the subject after which the displacement or voids of light are then transformed into varying depths. The scanner then reconstructs the object digitally, recreating 3-dimensional objects in a 2-dimensional plane by accounting for the reliefs of the subject and analyzing the deformation. The Revopoint POP 3D Scanner and Matter and Form V2 3D

Scanner are both structured-light scanners that use a small webcam in tandem with projectors to observe the distortion of horizontal and vertical bands of emitted rays. The collected individual scans are then merged; the Revopoint does so automatically (Revopoint, 2021), whereas the Matter and Form V2 3D Scanner must be operated manually using a base scan (Matter and Form, 2018). This process arguably gives more user input, but can also lead to shrunken or misaligned models. Photogrammetry operates on a similar principle by taking overlapping photos and stitching them together, based on camera location, distance, discernable features, and triangulation. All of these methods work on the same principle, gathering key points between observations or pictures and storing them in a dense point cloud. Once the capture of data is complete, the area in between the points is meshed with straight areas and a solid is formed. With more points, features like curves and complex geometries can be meshed with ease, whereas lesser points in the cloud lead to blocky or choppier features. This mesh can then be saved to other programs to be 3D printed.

Revopoint POP 3D

The Revopoint POP 3D scanner is a lightweight structured light scanner that detects features by introducing infrared light that safely bounces off the subject. The device is constructed of two IR sensors on each side of the camera with an RGB sensor for texture information (Revopoint, 2021). The device can be connected via USB A or USB C to a personal computer or mobile smartphone to power the device and transmit captured data. To use the Revopoint POP, two pieces of software were used: Handy Scan and Handy Studio (during the writing of this paper, Revopoint released a new suite of tools, including Revo Scan, Studio, and Calibrate, that were not available during the conceptual or data-collection phases of this report) (Revopoint, 2021). Handy Scan allows for communication between the scanner and the PC to collect data from the scanner, save the generated point cloud, or export a mesh to a Wavefront OBJ File or a Stanford Triangle Format (.obj or .ply, respectfully) format. Handy Studio is used to edit the saved .obj or .ply file, as it can mesh, clip, fill, smooth, mirror, and export the subject to a .stl format (Revopoint, 2021). The exported .stl file is then processed by Cura to print on the Ender 3.

The Revopoint POP 3D scanner offers five distinct modes of scanning: Features, Marker, Face, Body, and Dark/Hair. The Features mode scans objects with distinct shape features, such as sculptures or figures. Marker mode scans objects with fewer distinct features, such as flat boards, balls, or bowls. Markers must be distributed evenly on the subject as the scanner generates point cloud data from the pattern of adjacent markers. Face mode is used to scan human faces, where exposure and gain are set according to face skin reflectivity. Body mode is best at scanning human bodies with gain and exposure being set automatically for the subject. Dark mode, which has the added title of Hair, can scan some dark objects such as boxes and clothes but not objects such as black leather shoes that absorb most light. All of these are

available for the corresponding mobile phone version of Handy Scan, which connects over a local mobile phone's hotspot, except for the Marker mode. The scanner captures eight frames per second while operating and automatically merges the frames of data as it goes. The subject being scanned can be stationary or placed on the included turntable with fiducial targets that allow the subject to turn. In terms of editing, Handy Scan allows users to completely erase the entire scan or the latest grouping of frames. Handy Studio allows users to clip the model via a drawn plane, fill any voids either by a curved or planar surface, smooth a mesh, or mirror the mesh. The editing abilities of the software are limited in that it cannot select individual points. This tool would be useful for erasing one protruding error, as a small noise can break models rather than having to restart the scan from scratch if saved incorrectly.

The Matter and Form V2

The Matter and Form V2 scanner is a structured light scanner, akin to the Revopoint POP 3D, but implements the use of two Class 1 Lasers (as defined by IEC 60825-1:2007) (Matter and Form, 2018). The device is a foldable system with one portion folding out to reveal the built-in 7" (approximately 18 cm) turntable on one side and the laser/webcam assembly on the other. The scanning assembly is located on a threaded shaft that turns to raise to 9.8" (approximately 25 cm) and lower the scanner, as the subject turns incrementally to scan all sides. An additional stipulation, the object cannot weigh more than 6.6 lbs. (3.0 kg). The software MF Studio has settings to scan at five fixed height intervals and control the rotation of the table. Multiple scans are taken, cleaned, and merged. The resulting mesh can then be exported to .ply, .obj, or .stl formats locally. To merge, the user manually overlays a secondary scan over a base scan and aligns it to the best of his or her ability. Selecting a different base scan can result in different alignments. MF Studio can be upgraded using the software +Quickscan, an add-on that can limit scanning to one laser and rotate the turntable constantly during a scan. It can reduce a usual hour-long scan down to five minutes. This decreases the overall operating time, but leaves more noise to filter through after scanning.

The editing tools available are plentiful and helpful, as they offer a plentiful variety to control and reconfigure scans. The brush tool selects and deselects points that can be deleted (referred to as "cleaning"). The brush tool works akin to a laser or drill: it has a set radius and will bore through everything in its path. This can be resolved by turning the scan and deselecting points that are to be kept. The program also features an adjustable noise filter that can select points within a certain noise radius. Lastly, MF Studio contains three different cropping tools: a radial tool and two plane erasure tools. The radial tool narrows the selection radius of points the higher it is turned. The plane tools erase data from the lowest point up (upward plane) or erase data from the tallest point down (downward plane). Whereas the Revopoint POP 3D has five different modes for scanning a multitude of

surfaces, the Matter and Form V2 scanner has just one regular scan mode. Additionally, the instruction manual suggests avoiding metallic, reflective, clear, or dark surfaces, as they might not be captured.

Photogrammetry (3DF Zephyr Software)

Photogrammetry consists of three key components: photo, -gram, -metry. Photo relates to how the subject is recorded (via a photographic picture), the ending -gram refers to something being written or drawn, and the suffix -metry means to measure. In essence, photogrammetry means to measure the subject by connecting or drawing a series of images together. Any device capable of capturing and storing pictures can be used; in this current study, an Olympus OM-D E-M5II was used, due to its high resolution of 16 or 40 MP. While other methods have a stationary sensor or camera to observe a rotating object, photogrammetry involves rotating the camera while the subject remains stationary. The photos of a given subject are taken in an upwards spiral fashion, as it is optimal for capturing details in complex and obtuse geometries. With the ever-increasing resolution of cameras installed in smartphones, this method can be easily introduced to all who can upload photos to the program.

3DF Zephyr is a software package that takes the sequence of photos taken of a subject and searches for matches between each picture to build a 3D mesh (3DF Zephyr, 2022). The free version was used in this study, in spite of its limited editing and exporting tools, when compared to paid versions, and can only handle up to 50 pictures at a time for reconstruction. In constructing and meshing the point cloud data, any unpictured or sparsely photographed features will be tessellated, thus exaggerating the missing space, or making it appear jagged or abstract. To edit the generated model, 3DF Zephyr offers multiple smoothing options, filling holes selectively or being watertight, and a plethora of clipping tools. These clipping tools use a plane, a box, a polygonal boundary, points from the cloud, camera viewpoints, triangles, or colors to edit the subject. The program can quickly measure and display characteristics like distance, elevation change, and inclination. Measurements can be used to determine the scaling factor between the sample and the model and can help edit a mesh closer to real proportions. This method may potentially produce models with altered dimensions, due to its imprecision, but results can be improved by calibrating the camera used with a measuring rod.

Examples

The format of the following images will first show the subject before showing the digitized model from each method, with additional notes in the sequence: Revopoint POP 3D, Matter and Form V2, and finally photogrammetry. The first sample examined was a concrete cornice trim fragment chosen due to its low reflectivity, textured top and sides, and flat bottom that could rest on a turntable or observation platform. Figure 1 shows the subject.

(a) The original concrete cornice trim fragment.

(b) The Revopoint POP 3D model.

(c) The Matter and Form V2 model.

(d) The 3DF Zephyr model.

Figure 1. The first subject is a concrete cornice trim fragment, with digitized models.

The two structured light scanners, the Revopoint POP 3D and the Matter and Form V2, were used in conjunction with a box composed of a cardboard shell lined with black foam to perform scans. The black foam absorbed any light and limited outside interruptions. The box was light-sealed so that the uncovered sections of the cardboard box would not be detected by the scanners. The Revopoint POP 3D had no issues arise during the scanning process for this sample. The adjustable tripod holding the scanner made obtaining various views simple, as it was a matter of simply adjusting the level while the sample turned on the table. While the texture mapping made it harder to see the level of detail, the roughness of the rising middle section (denoted by the red solid circle in Figure 2) was more rounded than the real subject. In addition, the bottom-most groove (denoted by the blue dashed circle in Figure 2) was completely missing, making the model shorter than the sample by two millimeters. Figure 2 shows the model with highlights.

Figure 2. The Revopoint POP 3D model of the concrete cornice trim fragment with textures and highlighted sections.

The Matter and Form V2 scanner had no issues arise in the scanning of this piece. The sample was set on a wooden block

during the scanning process and then edited out afterward; this was done in order to allow for better capture of the subject's underside. The side grooves were softer than the previous sample, but show more detail in the middle rock section (once again denoted by a red solid circle in Figure 3), whereas the Revopoint POP 3D's model was overall rounder. Additionally, it had a more accurate height, but reduced width of approximately one to two millimeters along the profile. Figure 3 shows the digitized model from this scanner.

Figure 3. The Matter and Form V2 model of the concrete cornice trim fragment with highlights.

For photogrammetry, the sample was placed on a wooden observation platform with the photos taken in a circular and then rising pattern. The observation platform (a wooden stool) was used because it allowed the photographer to have easy rotation around the subject and allowed for the camera to have a constant radius away from the subject in the case of the circular pictures. The pattern allowed for the most capture of detail in the fewest number of pictures. 3DF Zephyr rejected no pictures and used all of the data in its reconstruction of this sample. In Figure 1 (d), some amounts of the wooden platform can be seen underneath the model, as the software filled the holes by drawing on old textures. The 3D printed model was significantly smaller than the original, at an estimated 75% scale of the original sample. What it lacks in dimensions, the model makes up for in detail as it has a greater level of detail than the Matter and Form V2 scanner's mesh. It can be complimented for its textures as seen in the figure, as it looks much closer to the original sample than the other models.

The next sample was a fragment of a tombstone statue that had a child holding onto an angel's hand. This sample was chosen due to its low reflectivity and more complex geometries and pits (in comparison to the concrete cornice trim). Figure 4 shows that the hand has a natural curved palm that leads to the clutched thumb: this is a natural location to check for tessellations in the scanners. While not easily seen, the fingers and curved surfaces have pits and chips that provide another spot to check for accuracy among the models.

(a) The sample concrete statue fragment.

(d) The 3DF Zephyr model.

(b) The Revopoint POP 3D model.

(c) The Matter and From V2 model.

Figure 4. The second subject is a concrete statue fragment with digitized models.

The Revopoint POP 3D had minimal issues arise during the process of scanning the fragment. The only inconvenience was that the tripod could not be placed so it could have an overhead view to catch the beneficial details of the model. To achieve this viewing angle, the operator picked up the tripod assembly and maneuvered it to the angles and recesses of the hand while the scanner was running. The final 3D print shows that minimal detail was lost and eradicated the texture coloring issue seen. Some noteworthy spots include exposed rocks and broken smoothed sections. Figure 4(b) shows the finished model with its off-color texturing. The Matter and Form V2 scanner had minimal issues in the scanning process as well. The limited motion of the table helped in some regards and hurt in others, as shorter scans allowed for faster data capturing. However, the mounted, nonadjustable camera led to issues orienting the sample to obtain more data in smaller parts; Figure 5 shows this in that the crease where the thumb and the palm meet has significant tessellation, and which can also be seen in the area encompassed by the red circle. Additionally, the fingers had tessellations along their digits and several of the pits and recesses were partially to mostly filled in the final print.

Figure 5. The Matter and Form V2 model with highlights around the tessellation between the thumb and the palm.

It was difficult to acquire photos of the hand statue fragment for photogrammetry. This was mostly due to the wooden stool having a recessed seat on which the fragment sat, allowing the sample to rock and become reoriented while taking pictures. To combat this problem, clay was introduced to the base of the hand to hold it upright, at the cost of detail at the base; Figure 6 shows this using the clay-filled hole that resulted in a crescent shape (shown with the yellow dashed circle) of data missing in the final model. Additionally, some major tessellations can be seen as fins sprouting on the backside of the model for no discernable reason. The final print also shows that the size was much closer to the original than the cornice trim. Additionally, there was significant tessellation due to 3DF Zephyr rejecting some data and the fact that black clay was used to hold the hand in an upright position. Some of the tessellations can be seen on the left side of Figure 6, where the black clay was removed along with the portion of the hand that contained rejected data.

Figure 6. Photogrammetry model of the concrete statue fragment with General/Deep Presets with highlighted lack of concise data due to clay.

The last set of samples analyzed for this study was a series of statues located around Western Kentucky University's campus: a rabbit statue, a book statue, a running fountain, and the school's mascot, Big Red. Figure 7 shows these along with some notes indicating that the inscription on the fountain is only in appearance and is not physically engraved. Due to its design, Matter and Form V2 could not scan these samples. While the Revopoint POP 3D scanner was marketed as useable indoors and out, in reality outdoor lighting conditions severely interfered with the infrared sensor. Scanning of these statues was attempted in sunny, cloudy, shaded, rainy, and snowy conditions but no data could be collected with the mobile or desktop version of the software. Future attempts to test Revopoint's abilities outdoors could include scanning at night or creating a dark environment by enveloping the sample in a dark box created with a hunting blind and black tablecloth.

(a) Chauncey Too by Jim Budish in 2007.

(b) "Books For Father" by Kevin Robb in 2008 outside of Gordon Wilson Hall.

(c) The Guthrie Fountain outside of Van Meter Hall.

(d) The Big Red statue sculpted by Russell Faxon in 1974.

Figure 7. Statues located around Western Kentucky University's campus.

Photogrammetry was able to handle all these statues with varying degrees of success. Figures 8-10 show the digitized rabbit statue, book statue, and fountain, while Figure 11 shows the effects of the different settings in 3DF Zephyr that facilitated differing Big Reds models. While the cornice trim and stone hand fragment were digitized using the "General" preset of settings, the outdoor setting and rejected photos from the data set led to the "Urban" preset. The first statue of rabbit statue Chauncey Too resulted in a satisfactory model, capturing details in the scenery, including the base with no

distortion of the statue's original shape. Figure 8 shows the model trimmed of the surrounding environment.

Figure 8. Chauncey Too model in 3DF Zephyr with Urban/Deep Presets.

The next statue, "Books For Father." was taken on the same day as the previous statue in similar weather conditions. However, their locations differed, as Chauncey Too was located in a dense section of trees that provided darker shading than the building shading "Books For Father." With these facts noted, the digitized model shows a significant level of detail with some minor discrepancies in the crevice where the two book "pages" meet and at the statue's base. Tessellation was present in the crevice of the pages resulting in a sphere, while the rest of the statue appeared as it otherwise did. Figure 9, at the bottom right corner, shows that the base has pits and jagged sections on all sides, likely due to the polished appearance of the base, which can be seen in Figure 7(b). Additionally, the "pages" were smooth on the sculpture whereas the final mesh was stippled and bumpy.

Figure 9. “Books For Father” model in 3DF Zephyr with Urban/Deep Presets.

Figure 10 shows that the Guthrie Fountain, photographed later in the afternoon, had several points of interest in the final model. To begin, the top four smaller columns supporting the topmost water-collecting dish are separated by gaps whereas the model has tessellated that area closed. This was due to a lack of data around each of the individual columns, which could be remedied by increasing the picture limit, but then would run the risk of getting the equipment wet. The next point of interest was the water, one of the most difficult entities to digitize, which was running during the series of photographs. It is present in the model but comes at the cost of engulfing some pipes and structures underneath it. The deep pit at the bottom right side of the fountain may be a product of the sun’s glare, resulting in erroneous data at this area alone. Aside from these issues, the texturing looks superb. The final 3D print of the fountain shows intricate details of the bottom column, ridges, and swirls. One detail that could not be recreated with much success was the lettering “Western Kentucky University.” As mentioned, the letters do not recess into the material and are thus harder to digitize, though it still makes a faint appearance in the final model.

Figure 10. Guthrie Fountain model in 3DF Zephyr with Urban/Deep Presets.

The next three models are used here in order to offer a brief explanation of 3DF Zephyr’s settings. When creating a project, the settings are selected from a variety of options before any operations can commence. There are three kinds of settings categories for users: Presets, Advanced, and Custom (Custom settings were disregarded for this study for clarity). In Presets, a user can select a category and the level of detail for that operation. Users can choose between preset categories of General, Ariel, Urban, Human body, Surface scan, and Vertical structures, followed by the presets Fast, Default, and Deep in order to control speed. The user can choose these settings for camera orientation, dense point cloud collection, and surface reconstruction. Each category has certain advantages and disadvantages when compared, depending on the subject matter of the photogrammetry. The Advanced options give a user more control of certain parameters in the digitizing process. As a trade, the more intense settings require more computing power and time. Figure 11 shows the models for the Big Red statue using photogrammetry. Several different settings were used, resulting in drastically different processing times, from five minutes to over an hour. The settings discussed here are those present in version 6.506 of 3DF Zephyr Free.

(a) Big Red model with General/Deep Presets.

(b) Big Red model with Urban/Deep Presets.

(c) Big Red model with Advanced Settings.

Figure 11. Big Red models made with different settings within 3DF Zephyr.

The first model of Big Red was run using General presets with Deep detail levels to capture as much detail as possible in the fastest time. The operation for Figure 11(a) ran for a total of five minutes. Some tessellations and odd texturing can be seen in the right armpit, right hand, and mouth; otherwise, this model is excellent. The software did not accept the entirety of the data provided, which may be a case for the issues listed above. The next model of Big Red, Figure 11(b), was run using Urban presets with Deep detail levels to capture as much detail as possible. The operation ran for a total of thirty minutes. This model fixed some of the issues of Figure 11(a), such as decreasing the tessellation of the right hand, right armpit, and mouth. However, the model is significantly thinner than the original statue, when turned to the side. No discernable reason can be given, as the program accepted more of the photo set with the Urban preset than the General preset. Additionally, some tessellation can be seen on top of the head. The last model of Big Red, Figure 11(c), was created using the Advanced settings by maxing out possible features, such as key point sensitivity, matching type, and matching stage depth, while leaving all other parameters at their defaults. The resulting operation ran for a total of one hour and fifteen minutes. As can be seen, the program created a giant chest cavity, an array of ghost faces, and an elongated mouth wrapped around its head. The top of the head appears to have extreme tessellation whereas the hands and fingers have been decreased to blobs. However, the backside of the Big Red model appears to be the best of the three. Additionally, the legs closely resemble the quality of the other two.

Conclusions

All of these methods excel in different areas of 3D scanning and modeling: resolution, ease of scanning, model clean-up, processibility, and portability. For medium to larger sample scans taken indoors, the Revopoint POP 3D scanner excels, as its feature recognition alignment saves ample time taking multiple scans as well as offers different modes for scanning different sample types. Matter and Form V2 excels at scanning small objects. Its included software cleans the model faster than every other method. But, for most situations, indoors or out and small to large samples, photogrammetry is the most accessible method of modeling in comparison to the other tools mentioned in this paper. However, it relies heavily on focused, high-resolution pictures to create accurate models. With the issues arising in digitizing real objects, any of these systems are still advantageous to other labor-intensive methods with their low price point and barrier of entry. The downfalls of these methods are nothing more than the limited technology available to users. However, research should be conducted to find the optimal settings for each sample and how lighting conditions impact the final model. Lastly, expanding the reach of this research to include the Custom settings of 3DF Zephyr could provide additional insight as to how each mode compares. The addition of a new suite of tools from Revopoint holds promise as well as it may address the limitations of the editing tools discussed in this paper.

This technology advances with every passing quarter. For instance, Creality will soon release the CR-Lizard Scanner, which could offer better, more affordable scanning to the community at large. Additionally, Epic Games and their acquired company, Capturing Reality, have announced plans to release the app RealityScan to the public, which allows users to create high-fidelity 3D models that could be implemented with the Unreal Engine (Epic Games Introduces RealityScan App, Now in Limited Beta, 2022). The last major development during the writing of this paper was the newly announced Nvidia 3D MoMa, an AI approach with inverse rendering that will allow for smooth implementation of user-generated models into graphic engines to change parameters such as material, light sources, and added physics (Salian, 2022).

Data Availability Statement

Data from this report, including photographs, digitized models, and Cura G-codes, will be made available upon request.

Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

- 3DF Zephyr (6.506). (2022). 3DFLOW. <https://www.3dflow.net/3df-zephyr-6-5-is-out-now/>
- Braam, D. (2022). Ultimaker Cura (4.13.1). Ultimaker. <https://ultimaker.com/learn/print-at-super-speed-with-ultimaker-cura-4-13/>
- Epic Games Introduces RealityScan App, Now in Limited Beta. (2022, April 4). Epic Games, Inc. <https://www.epicgames.com/site/en-US/news/epic-games-introduces-realityscan-app-now-in-limited-beta>
- Matter and Form. (2018). Matter and Form 3D Scanner V2 User Manual. https://matterandform.net/downloads/MF_Studio_User-Manual_EN.pdf?2018-05-14
- Revopoint. (2021). POP 3D SCANNER User Manual. https://www.revopoint3d.com/wp-content/uploads/download/Revopoint%20POP%20User%20Manual_V2.2.0.pdf

Salian, I. (2022, June 21). AI in the Big Easy: NVIDIA Research Lets Content Creators Improvise With 3D Objects. NVIDIA. <https://blogs.nvidia.com/blog/2022/06/21/inverse-rendering-3d-research-cvpr/>.

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